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Research Article

**IN VITRO ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY AND PLASMID
MEDIATED DRUG RESISTANCE IN METHICILLIN
RESISTANT *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS***

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Abstract:

The emergence of multidrug resistance of human pathogenic bacteria and many undesirable adverse effects of antibiotics has led to a search for new antimicrobial agents. In this study, to screen the Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) from clinical specimens, 58 samples were collected from the government and private hospitals in Namakkal District, Tamil Nadu, India. Among 58 samples, 42 were identified as genus *Staphylococcus*. Out of 42 isolates, 16 were Coagulase positive. Based on the selective medium, differential medium and biochemical characters, 4 isolates were confirmed as MRSA. The antibacterial activity of selected heavy metals and different antibiotics were carried out by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. Among the tested 8 heavy metals, copper sulphate and mercury chloride showed resistance to all 4 MRSA. Out of 15 antibiotics tested Penicillin and Nalidixic acid are resistant to all four MRSA isolates. Tetracycline was resistant to MRSA₀₁, Chloramphenicol was resistance to MRSA₀₂ and Erythromycin resistant to MRSA₀₃. The four isolates of MRSA were processed for the isolation of plasmid DNA. For testing the capability of spreading drug resistance in plasmid, done by transformation using five methicillin resistance genetic strains of *Escherichia coli* such as MTCC119, KRX, DH₅α, HB101 and GJ1158. The methicillin resistance in plasmid was confirmed by DH₅α and GJ1158 transformants.

Keywords: Antibacterial Activity, Methicillin Resistance, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Plasmid DNA, Heavy Metals

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INTRODUCTION:

Staphylococcus has been mainly reported as a major cause of community and hospital acquired infections. These genus consists of at least 32 species which includes *Staphylococcus aureus* has special significance as a pathogen able to cause a variety of different kinds of infections [1]. It can produce a wide variety of diseases, such as tonsillitis, cellulites, deep abscesses, osteomyelitis, pneumonia, sepsis and endocarditis, which are mediated by the secretion of toxins [2]. Over the past 30 years, molecular and genetic dissection of *S. aureus* has revealed a great number of target tissues, and secreted enzymes and toxins that are responsible for infection and distant disease [3]. *Staphylococcus* species can be identified on the basis of a variety of conventional phenotypic characters. In addition, species can be identified on the basis of molecular phenotypic properties such as cellular fatty acids, multilocus enzyme electrophoresis, whole cell polypeptides and genotypic properties such as chromosome restriction fragments, macro restriction patterns and ribotypes [4].

Approximately 20% of healthy people are persistent carriers, 60% are intermittent and 20% are non-carriers. Most infants become colonized shortly after birth, but carriage decreases with age. In many people the pattern of carriage changes between the ages of 10 to 20 years. *Staphylococci* are also can transmit from person to person upon transmission the organism may become established as part of the recipient's normal flora and later be introduced to sterile sites by trauma or invasive procedures. The person to person of *Staphylococci* particularly those that have acquired antimicrobial resistance, most notably occurs in hospitals and presents substantial infection control problems [5].

Treatment of *Staphylococcus aureus* infection showing no signs of broad-antibiotic resistance is achieved with a cocktail of antibiotics, including some of the following: flucloxacillin, Gentamycin, Rifampicin, fusidic acid, erythromycin, Vancomycin and cefotaxime. However, 90% of *S. aureus* strains are penicillin resistant [6]. Methicillin was introduced in 1959 to treat infections caused by penicillin resistant *Staphylococci*. In 1961, there were reports of artificial induction of methicillin resistance in *Staphylococci* and by 1963 there appeared the first infections with Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). The mutation in the *mecA* gene of *Staphylococcus* will provide resistance to all beta-lactams [7]. This gene codes for penicillin binding protein-A, mutation in the gene prevents penicillin from effectively binding foreign particles. Resistance to beta-lactams is tested by exposing a bacterial culture to Oxacillin. If the bacterium is resistant to Oxacillin, it will be

resistant to all beta-lactams, and quite possibly also resistant to Erythromycin, Gentamycin, Tetracycline and Clindamycin [8]. Community isolates of MRSA tend to be susceptible to a variety of non- beta-lactam antibiotics, whereas HA-MRSA are typically resistant to multiple antibiotics. Other differences are that genotypes of community isolates are not the same as those of health care derived isolated, community strains harbor a novel methicillin resistance cassette gene element not identify to date among strains that are endemic to health care setting, and community isolates occur in patients lacking typical risk factors for MRSA [9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Collection of Clinical Samples**

A total of 58 wound swab samples were collected from the individuals including in and out patients of private and government hospitals in Namakkal district, Tamil Nadu for the isolation of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). The sterile cotton swabs were used for collection of wound swab sample. All the collected wound swab samples were placed in separate sterile tube containing sterile saline. The swabs were carefully transported to the laboratory with in 30 min for further processing.

Isolation of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

The collected clinical wound swab samples were inoculated on selective and differential medium to isolate the *Staphylococcus aureus* includes Mannitol salt agar and Blood agar medium. The further confirmation of *S. aureus* was performed by Gram Staining, Coagulase Test (Slide and Tube method), Catalase test, Oxidase test, DNase test, Carbohydrate Fermentation Test, Acetoin Production Test, Nitrate Reduction Test, Growth at 10% NaCl. The typical Coagulase positive organisms were inoculated on the MeReSa agar (HiMedia, Mumbai) plate and incubated at 18-24 hours for selection and identification of MRSA. The selected MRSA colonies from MeReSa Agar plate were subcultured in nutrient broth.

Antibacterial Activity of Heavy Metals and Detergents

The antibacterial sensitivity test was done using the MRSA isolates against heavy metals and detergents by Kirby- Bauer disc diffusion method. The following heavy metals and detergents were used to evaluate the antimicrobial activity includes, Mercury chloride, Silver nitrate, Zinc sulfate, Copper sulfate, Potassium iodide, Xylenol and Tween 20. The stocks were prepared by dissolving 50mg of each compound in 1ml sterile distilled water. 150µl of stock solution added to the sterile Whatmann No.1 filter paper disc aseptically and allowed to dry. The Muller Hinton Agar (MHA)

plates were prepared. The isolates were swabbed evenly on the surface of the medium using sterile cotton swabs. The inoculum was allowed to dry for about 3 to 5 minutes. Then the prepared discs were placed on the agar using sterile forceps. After placing the discs, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The zone of inhibition was recorded after the incubation period.

Antibacterial Activity of Different Antibiotics

The antibiotic susceptibility test was performed by Kirby- Bauer disc diffusion method. The following antibiotics were used for the antibacterial activity. These includes, Amikacin (30µg), Amoxicillin (30µg), Chloramphenicol (30µg), Erythromycin (15µg), Gentamycin (10µg), Kanamycin (30µg), Levofloxacin (5µg), Methicillin (5µg), Nalidixic acid (30µg), Neomycin (30µg), Norfloxacin (10µg), Ofloxacin (5µg), Penicillin G (10U), Rifampicin (5µg), Streptomycin (10µg), Tetracycline (30µg), Oxacillin (10µg), Rifampicin (10µg) and Vancomycin (10µg). The Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates were prepared. The isolates were swabbed evenly on the surface of the medium using sterile cotton swabs. The inoculum was allowed to dry for about 3 to 5 minutes. Then the antibiotic discs were placed on the agar using sterile forceps. After placing the discs, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The zone of inhibition was recorded after the incubation period.

Isolation of Plasmid DNA from MRSA Isolates

10 ml of overnight culture of MRSA isolates was taken in a centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 5000 rpm at 4°C for 10 minutes. The pellet was resuspended in 200µl of solution I and 10µl of lysosyme. Then the content was mixed well and incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. 200µl of solution II was added and incubated at 37°C for 10 minutes. 200µl of solution III was added and incubated at 4°C for 10 minutes and the content was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. Supernatant was taken and equal volume of phenol: chloroform (1:1) was added and mixed well. The Content was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. Aqueous layer was taken and 0.1 volume of sodium acetate was added followed by 0.7 volume of isopropanol and centrifuged at 12000 rpm at 4°C for 10 minutes. Pellet was resuspended with 1 ml of 70 % ethanol and centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. The pellet was taken (plasmid DNA) and resuspended in 20µl of TE buffer and the Plasmid was confirmed by 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis.

Transformation by *Escherichia coli*

The methicillin-sensitive *Escherichia coli* genetic strains were selected as host for transformation (MTCC119, HB101, KRX, DH₅α, and GJ1158). The host strains were subcultured in 5ml of LB

broth and kept incubated for overnight. 0.5ml of overnight culture was taken and inoculated into 50ml of LB broth and incubated until the culture reach 10⁸ cells /ml (O.D 0.6 at 600nm). The cells were recovered by centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was removed and the pellet resuspended with 10ml of 0.1M ice cold calcium chloride solution and kept it in ice for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5minutes. The supernatant was removed and the pellet resuspended in 2.5ml of 0.1M ice cold calcium chloride solution and kept it in ice for 30minutes. 10µl of plasmid DNA isolated from MRSA were added and kept it in ice for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, the mixture was placed in a preheated water bath for 1minute at 90°C and immediately transferred to ice for 1-2 minutes. 800µl of sterile LB broth was added to all the tubes and incubated for 90 minutes at 37°C in shaking water bath. Then, 0.1ml of culture was taken and spread over the methicillin containing plate to select the transformants.

RESULTS:

A total 58 wound swab samples have been processed to find out the *Staphylococcus aureus* on selective and differential medium. Out of 58 isolates, 42 were shown typical positive *S. aureus* growth on Mannitol salt agar and blood agar medium. A colour change from red to yellow was around the growth on Mannitol salt agar were observed. On blood agar, a clear (β-type) hemolysis around the colony was observed. All the 42 isolates were subjected for coagulase test, to differentiate coagulase positive and negative *Staphylococcus*. Out of 42 isolate, 16 isolates were shown coagulase positive. The inoculum of agar coagulase positive *Staphylococcus aureus* were plated on MeReSa medium to select the MRSA isolates, out of 16 isolates, 4 were resistance to methicillin (MRSA₀₁, MRAS₀₂, MRSA₀₃ and MRSA₀₄). All four MRSA isolate were further subjected for identification by using various test, such as microscopy and biochemical tests. The result have been shown in the Table-1.

Antibiotic test was performed by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method against four MRSA isolates. Antimicrobial activity of heavy metals and detergents have been shown in the Table-2 and Fig-I. The antibacterial activity of different antibiotic discs has been shown in Table-3 and Fig-II. From the selected isolates, the plasmid was obtained and it was confirmed by agarose gel electrophoresis. The results have been shown in Fig-III. The methicillin-resistance in plasmid was confirmed by bacterial transformation in genetic host (*E. coli*) strains DH₅α and GJ1158. The results hhave been shown in Fig-IV.

Table 1 Identification of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

S.No	Tests	Results
1.	Growth on Mannitol Salt Agar	Positive (Yellow colour colony)
2.	Growth on Blood Agar	Positive (β -Hemolysis)
3.	Coagulase Test	Positive
4.	Growth on MeReSa Agar	Positive (Greenish Blue colour colony)
5.	Grams reaction	Positive cocci
6.	Catalase	Positive
7.	Oxidase	Negative
8.	DNase	Positive
9.	Carbohydrate Fermentation Test	
	Glucose	Acid / No gas
	Maltose	Acid / No gas
	Lactose	Acid / No gas
	Sucrose	Acid / No gas
	Mannitol	Acid / No gas
10.	Nitrate Reduction Test	Positive
11.	Acetoin Production Test	Positive
12.	Growth at 10% NaCl	Positive

Table 2 Antibacterial activity of Heavy Metals and Detergents

S No	Name of Heavy metals and detergents	Resistance /Sensitive			
		MRSA ₀₁	MRSA ₀₂	MRSA ₀₃	MRSA ₀₄
1.	Potassium iodide	R	R	R	R
2.	Copper sulphate	S	S	S	S
3.	Silver nitrate	R	R	R	R
4.	Iodine	R	R	R	R
5.	Mercury chloride	S	S	S	S
6.	Zinc sulphate	R	R	R	R
7.	Xylene	R	R	R	R
8.	Tween 20	R	R	R	R

Fig 1. Antibacterial Activity of Heavy Metals and Detergents against MRSA Clinical Isolates

Table 3 Antibacterial Activity of different antibiotics

S No	Name of Antibiotics	Disc Conc	Resistance /Sensitive			
			MRSA ₀₁	MRSA ₀₂	MRSA ₀₃	MRSA ₀₄
1.	Amikacin	30 µg	S	S	S	S
2.	Amoxicillin	30 µg	S	S	S	S
3.	Chloramphenicol	30 µg	S	S	S	S
4.	Erythromycin	15 µg	R	S	R	S
5.	Gentamycin	10 µg	S	S	R	R
6.	Kanamycin	30 µg	R	R	R	R
7.	Levofloxacin	5 µg	S	S	S	S
8.	Methicillin	5 µg	R	R	R	R
9.	Nalidixic acid	30 µg	R	R	R	R
10.	Neomycin	30 µg	S	S	S	S
11.	Norfloxacin	10 µg	S	S	S	S
12.	Ofloxacin	5 µg	S	S	S	S
13.	Penicillin G	10 U	R	R	R	R
14.	Streptomycin	10 µg	S	S	S	S
15.	Tetracycline	20 µg	R	S	S	R
16.	Oxacillin	10 µg	R	R	R	R
17.	Rifampicin	10 µg	S	S	S	S
18.	Vancomycin	10 µg	R	R	R	R

(Note: Results based on National committee for clinical Laboratory standards)

Fig II. Antibacterial Activity of Antibiotics against MRSA Clinical Isolates

(MRSA₀₁, MRSA₀₂, MRSA₀₃ & MRSA₀₄)

Fig III. Isolation of Plasmid DNA confirmed by Agarose Gel Electrophoresis.

DH5α

GJ1158

Fig IV. Methicillin-resistance in plasmid by bacterial transformation in genetic host (*E. coli*) strains DH5α and GJ1158.

DISCUSSION:

During the past years, especially hospital associated strains have developed multi-resistance to antibiotics. Clinical microbiological diagnostic must pay attention to correct identification of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and reliable detection of resistance characteristic in particular of those with heterogeneous phenotypic expression. MRSA strains are often isolated from nosocomial identification of *S. aureus* and have become widespread in hospital. Recently new strains of MRSA have emerged in community [10]. In many bacterial species, plasmid is responsible for a particular type of gene transfer between cells, a property that accounted for the initial interest in plasmids in the 1950s. Similar to phages, plasmids heavily depend on the metabolic functions of the host cell for their reproduction. R-plasmids make the host cell resistant to one or more antibiotics and many R-plasmids can transfer the resistant to cells

lacking R. R-plasmids confer resistance on their host cell to a variety of fungal antibiotics and are usually self-transmissible. Most R-plasmids consists of two contiguous segments of DNA. One of these segments called Resistance Transfer Factor

(RTF) and other segment called the R-determinant, variable in size and carries gene for antibiotic resistance.

The present study was taken to check the drug resistance of MRSA coded by either chromosomal DNA or plasmid DNA. It is well known that nasal carriage of MRSA is an important risk factor for transmission of bacterium in community hospitals [11, 12]. In this study, the samples were taken from wound for isolation of drug resistance MRSA. Coagulase-negative *Staphylococci* differ phenotypically from *Staphylococcus aureus* by their lack of ability to form some extra-cellular products and cell-wall associated proteins. The

coagulase test-tube reaction has been used as the main species characteristic of *S. aureus*, as has DNase formation in food Microbiology. Although less sensitive and less specific than coagulase formation and the demonstration of clumping factor is often used in routine clinical microbiology [13]. In our present study 16 isolated out of 42 shows Coagulase positive.

Mannitol Salt Agar is a selective medium for NaCl-tolerant bacterial species such as *Staphylococcus* and *Enterococci*. Mannitol fermentation is a species characteristic of *Staphylococcus aureus* in contrast to *S. epidermidis*. However a number of other coagulase negative species, For eg., *S. haemolyticus* are also able to form acid from mannitol, this biases the use of mannitol salt agar for MRSA screening on blood agar MRSA produced β -type hemolysis [14]. ORSA agar from OXOID, containing oxacillin, NaCl, Polymixin B and aniline dye blue as indicator for mannitol fermentation detects hetero resistant MRSA with exclusion of BORSA, however, it needs 48hours incubation at 37°C [15]. In this report, we have also used MeReSa Agar base with supplement (FD229) for the confirmation of MRSA from clinical specimens. Out of 16 CPS 4 isolates were identified as MRSA.

The sections of a cloned 27kb segment of chromosomal DNA, associated with mercury and tetracycline resistance genes and flanking repeats associated with methicillin-resistance on the chromosome of *S. aureus* [16]. A series of new amphiphilic cationic quinine- derived compounds were synthesized and characterized. It appears that Q3 and Q7 may be able to maintain good antibacterial activity against most pathogenic bacteria. Interestingly, the two amphiphilic cationic quinine-derived compounds have good activity against methicillin-sensitive and MRSA from clinical isolates [17]. In this present investigation, the antimicrobial activities of heavy metals against 4 MRSA isolates were carried out. Out of 6 metals and 2 detergents, copper sulphate and mercury chloride shows sensitivity towards all isolates. Assay for antibiotic sensitivity are routine standard procedure in all microbiology laboratory and they represent a commonly used marker for MRSA phenotyping.

The total of 72 MRSA was collected from the university hospital in Monastir. Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern revealed that MRSA strains were resistant to kanamycin (88.9%), tetracycline (61%), erythromycin (30.5%), fusidic acid (38.8%), and gentamycin (25%). All MRSA were susceptible to pristinamycin, vancomycin and leicoplain. MICs determination showed that 73.61% of *S. aureus* had oxacillin MICs >

256 μ g/ml likewise in our present study 4 clinical isolates of MRSA was subjected to 18 antibiotics to test their susceptibility [18]. Kanamycin, methicillin, oxacillin, vancomycin, and nalidixic acid were resistant to all isolates. MRSA₀₁ and MRSA₀₄ were resistant to tetracycline, and the erythromycin is resistant to MRSA₀₁ and MRSA₀₃. This result shows their slight variation in drug resistance.

Resistance to β -lactamase resistant penicillins or Methicillin-resistance depends on a complex expression mechanism of the *MecA* gene, which is often species-idiosyncratic among *Staphylococci* [19]. The Methicillin resistant *Staphylococci* is determined by *mecA* resides on mobile genetic elements of chromosomal cassette-*mec*-CSCS *mec* [20]. Antibiotic resistance is more likely caused by the uptake of elements carrying resistance gene [21]. In 1999, Tn1546 like elements in *Enterococci* to vancomycin-resistance [22]. Resistance factor are associated with mobile genetic elements, such as Transposons or conjugative plasmids [23].

In *Aeromonas salmonicida* R-plasmids mediate Oxytetracycline (OT) resistance [24]. Antibiotic resistance gene can reside on self-replicative extrachromosomal plasmids [25, 26]. Plasmid carriage plays an important role in antibiotic resistance, especially in Multidrug-resistant Hospital-acquired MRSA and community-acquired MRSA. Based on the above findings, plasmids were isolated from all 4 isolates and confirmed by agarose gel electrophoresis. This provides the convincing evidence that the plasmid may code for antibiotic resistance. Shuttle vector (pgc2) which carries multiple cloning sites and with insets of *Staphylococcal* DNA up to 10Kb in size, yield large amounts of super coiled DNA from *E. coli* transformants. These high yields of DNA are sufficient to obtain satisfactory transformation frequencies with *Staphylococcus aureus* protoplasts [27, 28].

To conclude the present study, the isolated plasmids were transferred to various genetic strains of *E. coli*, which are susceptible to methicillin and the transformants were selected by plating on methicillin medium. Tested 5 strains of *E. coli* DH5 α and GJ1158 acquired the methicillin resistance characters. It is widely accepted that plasmid DNA may confer antibiotic resistance and therefore it might be assumed that MRSA isolates would carry additional plasmids compared to normal *Staphylococcus aureus* with a less resistance phenotype. In conclusion the present observation indicate that the weakness of the analysis of bacterial strains by plasmid profiling is inherent to the fact that plasmids are mobile extra chromosomal elements that can be lost or acquired easily thus it is well known that epidemiologically related strains can exhibit different plasmid profile.

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